

**PAKIKIBAKA SA PANAHOON NG WALANG KATIYAKAN: EXPLORATORY
STUDY ON THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF FILIPINO
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Pakikibaka sa Panahon ng Walang Katiyakan: Exploratory Study on the Lived Experiences of Filipino Student Activist

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Abstract

This investigation delves into the phenomena of 'pakikibaka', a term denoting collective struggle, among student activists within the current political context of the Philippines, a landscape marred by misinformation and skewed public perceptions. Despite the initial high trust ratings for the current administration, as reported by the 2022 Pulse Asia Survey, a discernible erosion in public confidence was observed by 2023 and 2024, with the decline largely attributed to the government's perceived failures in addressing critical socio-economic challenges. Particular emphasis is placed on the student population, a demographic significantly impacted by recent budget cuts in the education sector, historical distortion, and widespread oppression and red-tagging, catalyzing a heightened sense of uncertainty and prompting this exploratory inquiry. Employing 'pakikipagkwentuhan', an indigenous qualitative methodology centered on conversational engagement, this research facilitates an unreserved discourse, enabling participants to express freely their insights predicated on their lived experiences. The study encompasses six enrolled student activists, all of whom are integrally affiliated with various mass organizations, are a minimum of 18 years of age, and self-identify as left-wing activists. The research findings demonstrate the perception of the experience of student activists. Central to the study's outcome is the conceptualization of 'pakikibaka' as a tool for recognizing the experiences of the marginalized sectors and advocating for their fundamental rights. Such engagement enhances their empathic understanding of the struggles of their 'kapwa' and articulates their advocacies through multifarious expressive modalities, encompassing writing, visual arts, and music, among others.

Keywords: *pakikibaka, student activist, pakikipagkapwa, pakikipagkwentuhan*

Introduction

Rooted in the intricate tapestry of historical and socio-political dichotomies, the genesis of Filipino society can be traced to the conflict between different classes that continue to shape its structural and superstructural facets. Despite its sovereignty in the post-colonial era, the Philippines grapples with multifaceted pressures both from within and from significant international players such as the United States of America and the People's Republic of China. These pressures influence various domains, encompassing economic policies, political decisions, cultural exchanges, military cooperation, and foreign diplomatic relations.

Further compounding the societal stratification are dominant local entities, notably the big local corporations and landlords, whose economic leverage and political influence perpetuate a hegemonic status quo. This invariably precipitates conflicts between the lower and upper classes, manifesting in agrarian disputes and labor tensions, particularly as the marginalized sectors strive for fundamental human and socio-economic rights. Such systemic conflicts often catalyze various forms of 'pakikibaka' (struggle), ranging from organized public demonstrations to the more radical approach of armed insurgency.

The current political climate in the Philippines is marked by a sense of uncertainty, further intensified by widespread misinformation and a tendency to misrepresent individuals and organizations engaged in pakikibaka. Activists frequently encounter the unjust categorization of being labeled as "dilawan" (affiliates of the liberal party), "komunista" (members of the Communist Party of the Philippines, CPP), or associated with the "NPA" (New People's Army, the armed wing of the CPP), irrespective of their actual affiliations or ideological orientations. This socio-political landscape has set the stage for the ascendancy of the current administration (Arugay, 2022).

Although the recent Pulse Asia Survey (2022) shows a high trust rating during the initial months of the current administration, there is a noticeable public dissatisfaction over the government's response in addressing critical socio-economic issues. These encompass rapidly increasing inflation, slow wage growth, unfavorable employment figures, and widespread poverty. The Philippine Statistics Authority (2022) underscored this economic quagmire, highlighting an inflation rate that soared to 7.7% and an unprecedented depreciation in the peso-dollar exchange rate (Cabuenas, 2022).

Although this economic downturn is not limited to the Philippines alone, the apparent lack of responsiveness from the government has resulted in significant dissatisfaction among the people, culminating in mass mobilizations. The student demographic, significantly imperiled by budgetary cuts in State Colleges and Universities (SUCs), the contentious proposition of a National Citizen Service Training Program (NCSTP) which is dubbed as a compulsory ROTC program, historical distortion, plans to amend the constitution (dubbed as Cha-Cha or Charter Change), and rampant campus repression, has been particularly vocal in its dissent. These issues have galvanized various protests, both virtual (due to the recent COVID-19 restrictions) and in person, involving different stakeholders, including students, student unions, faculties, and administrative personnel.

Pakikibaka is conceptualized as a collective struggle (Enriquez, 1992), necessitating solidarity ('pakikisama') against a common adversarial force. This principle serves as a catalyst for the 'anakpawis' (toiling masses) in their pursuit of fundamental rights and resistance against the oppressive hegemony of the 'ibang-tao' (ruling classes) or those in positions of power ('nasa may kapangyarihan'). This dynamic is pervasive among various societal sectors, including agrarian communities advocating for land rights and governmental support, labor forces demanding just and humane working conditions and remunerations, and student bodies championing an educational paradigm that is scientific, nationalistic, and mass-oriented. Enriquez (1992), as cited by Pe-Pua and Protacio-Marcelino (2000), identified pakikibaka as one of the confrontative surface values, a notion corroborated by Yacat (2013), who posited that pakikibaka, along with other confrontative values like 'bahala na' and 'lakas ng loob', are indispensable in the articulation of individual and collective rights.

This research endeavor aims to delve into these complex interplay of power, resistance, and societal change in contemporary Filipino society, particularly among Filipino student activists, providing an academically rigorous exploration of the manifestations and implications of pakikibaka in shaping the nation's socio-political trajectory.

Research Questions

This research aimed to investigate the experiences of student activists who are currently engaging in Pakikibaka. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. How do student activists define pakikibaka?
2. What are the factors considered by the participants in their pakikibaka?
3. How do the pakikibaka of the student activist affect their experiences:
 - 3.1. as a student;
 - 3.2. as an individual; and
 - 3.3. as a member of society?
4. What are the hopes and aspirations of the student activists in engaging with their pakikibaka during this current political sphere?

Methodology

Research Design

The research utilized qualitative research, offering an interpretative framework crucial for an in-depth exploration of the subjective experiences of student activists in the Philippines. Central to this approach was the employment of 'Pakikipagkwentuhan', an indigenous method facilitating informal yet profound dialogues, thereby allowing a rich understanding of the participants' 'pakikibaka' through narratives drawn from their personal perspectives and experiences (Orteza, 1997).

Participants

Combined snowball and purposive sampling approaches to select its participants were used. Initially, snowball sampling was used to tap into different mass organizations through referrals from initial contacts. Subsequently, purposive sampling was applied to ensure candidates met specific inclusion criteria: being at least 18 years old, actively enrolled in an academic institution, and engaged in student activism for a minimum of six months. A distinctive focus was placed on left-wing activists, although the specific nature of their socio-political engagements was not a selection determinant.

Instruments

The study approach was systematically structured into a series of interconnected phases. The research process was initiated by developing a research instrument, including the development of guiding questions that were aligned with the research objectives. This instrument underwent a rigorous evaluation process by a panel of experts to ensure its efficacy in generating meaningful responses.

Procedure

Pakikipagkwentuhan was utilized during the data acquisition phase. Before this, pilot interviews were undertaken to assess the validity and reliability of the questions. The researchers conducted preliminary visits to the participants in order to establish a relationship and establish a trusting environment. The data collection process adhered to strict health and safety procedures, which encompassed the implementation of precautions such as social distancing and vaccination requirements. The duration of the interviews varied between 60 and 90 minutes, after which a debriefing session was conducted to clarify the subsequent procedural steps and data handling processes.

Data obtained from Pakikipagkwentuhan were subjected to semantic transcription, where emphasis was placed on capturing the conceptual essence of the discourse over a literal transcription. To uphold ethical research practices, all personal identifiers were removed from the transcripts. Thematic analysis, guided by a framework provided by Brikci & Green (2007), was the chosen method for dissecting the data. The analytical phase was iterative and included feedback from participants to ensure authenticity.

Ethical Considerations

Foremost in this study was the stringent adherence to ethical standards. Participants' anonymity was paramount, acknowledging potential risks associated with activism in the Philippines' current political climate. Confidentiality was rigorously maintained, with data access severely restricted to relevant stakeholders. Assurance was provided that any future dissemination of findings would preserve participant anonymity, thereby safeguarding them from potential retribution or harm.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with responses made by the student activist to the questions made for the study: (1) the activists' conceptualization of 'pakikibaka'; (2) the determinants of their engagement; (3) the impact of 'pakikibaka' on their personal, academic, and societal facets; and (4) their aspirations within the current political sphere.

PAKIKIBAKA, AS DEFINED BY STUDENT ACTIVIST

The term 'pakikibaka', as expounded upon by student activists, is a complex and context-specific notion that gives rise to various understandings and implications. The term elicits introspection, and its significance differs depending on an individual's distinct life experiences and circumstances. The comprehension of 'pakikibaka' is inherently shaped by an individual's personal context, and it can also be influenced by the perspectives and attitudes prevalent within the wider social environment.

Pakikibaka as a means to aid the marginalized and fight for the masses

'Pakikibaka' encompasses a complex and diverse set of principles embraced by student activists, who are dedicated to supporting marginalized communities and advocating the welfare of the people. This term defies a singular, universally accepted definition, as its interpretation is inherently contingent upon individual experiences and perspectives.

"...para sa akin yung pakikibaka yung pag-champion ng mga panawagan na mas nakakabuti sa kalidad ng pamumuhay ng mga manggagawa...ng mga marginalized sector..." - SA 0001

The student activists involved in this endeavor are not motivated by material things. Rather, they have a collective objective to help the marginalized and foster their comprehension of the necessity of this movement. One of the reasons behind this action is to enable activists to gain firsthand experience of the circumstances or way of life of the people. Student activists play a role in amplifying the voices of oppressed people and those who have historically been silenced.

"...hindi naman po ako kumikilos o nakikibaka para sa sarili ko. Wala po akong hinahanap na makuha pero...hindi po talaga ako naghahanap pero along the way may nahahanap ako na kunwari a-attend ako ng BMI hindi naman para sa sarili ko para alam ko na malaking tulong talaga to para sa masa. Makakatulong to sakin kasi maliliwanagan ako na ahh ito pala yung nararanasan ng masa." -SA 0002

"...wala po kaming nakukuha... pero ang nakukuha po namin is mass is parang connection ng pakikibaka sa masa...kasi talagang sa pagiging aktibista itatapon mo lahat ng expectation mo na maging mayaman...sumikat...tinatapon na natin yan..." - SA 0004

The essence of 'pakikibaka' transcends mere observation. It signifies active engagement and solidarity with the masses. Activists guide social observers and reveal the realities we have today.

"...yung pagsusuri ng ating lipunan syempre diba base muna sa teorya ano ba ang kalagayan o sitwasyon ng ating bansa ngayon at dito tayo hahango ng ating praktika...so dito na yung action part naman ng pakikibaka pero syempre ginagabayan tayo ng pagsusuring panlipunan bago magkaroon nga ng pakikibaka.." - SA 0003

Pakikibaka as a means of understanding their Kapwa

'Pakikibaka', as a central tenet of activism, serves as a means for individuals to engage in a collective exploration of their 'Kapwa'. This concept emphasizes the recognition of the unique experiences of all participants, viewing each experience as valuable and worthy of consideration. Furthermore, 'pakikibaka' involves the systematic analysis of complex societal experiences that often require immediate solutions. At its core, the essence of activism lies in comprehending the multifaceted dimensions of the masses, empathizing with their challenges, and nurturing a commitment to ameliorate their conditions.

"...Nagkakaroon po nang collective struggle, nagpapamuhay po tayo sa masa naintindihan po natin yung pinaka-conditions na meron sila and in return po labanan yung system na nagpapahirap sa kanila...Yung pakikibaka po talaga...yung pinaka-firm na notion po nito is para po talaga sa masa." - SA 0004

Pakikibaka as means to organize different programs

'Pakikibaka' serves as a strategic means for orchestrating various programs aimed at achieving societal transformation. The pursuit of an organized and coordinated movement has led to the formulation of initiatives such as Arouse-Organize-Mobilize (AOM). The primary objective of AOM is to disseminate knowledge regarding individuals' aspirations and to facilitate their realization of the collective desire for transformative change. The efficacy of such endeavors hinges upon collaborative efforts, with the premise that

collective engagement is more likely to yield success when it is underpinned by a shared vision, passion, and unwavering commitment.

"...paglaban at may ginagamit po kami na acronym na Arouse-Organize-Mobilize or AOM na i-educate ang mga ibang tao tungkol sa pinaglalaban at mag organisa, magsama-sama pa kasi hindi lang maa-attain ang pakikibaka kung mag-isa lang ako. Kailangan may kasama o collective at organisado at pangatlo, mobilize...kumilos para ma-attain ang mga goals ng isa't-isa" - SA 0002

It is noteworthy that the advocacy for the masses, as a central facet of activism, seeks to redress the prevailing power imbalance, where the powerful occupy the upper level of society while those at the bottom suffer systemic oppression. In light of this, one of the core aims of 'pakikibaka' is to provide exemplary service to those deserving of it, acknowledging their fundamental role in fostering societal change:

"...evident naman po talaga na ang daming marami po talagang nahihirapan at titingnan po natin ang tatsulok na 99% po tayo ay nao-oppress ng gobyerno 1% lang po ang nakikinabang kaya para sa masa kasi ang masa rin po talaga ang tutulong sa pagbabago. Hindi po kami kung hindi ang masa kaya ngayon todo educate po kami at pagkilos para matulungan hindi lang tayo pati ang masa." - SA 0002

The accounts of student activists reflect a sense of optimism, with initiatives that were initially perceived as challenging yields positive outcomes. These accounts signal a trajectory toward meaningful societal transformation. Even in cases where some individuals may not immediately grasp the full extent of their dreams and aspirations, there is an acknowledgment that the benefits will eventually extend to many.

"...Tapos ayon meron din kaming napa pakatan,... ayon masaya siya kasi, andami rin nakapag recruit din kami sa masa...ganyan tapos nakapag mulat talaga lalo sa kabataan...ganon tapos parang yun din ang naging unang hakbang ko para ano na maging organisador ngayon meron na din akong nabuong org. napapakilos ko na ganyan..." - SA 0005

Pakikibaka as an Expression in Different Forms

'Pakikibaka' is not confined to protests as its sole expression. Rather, it manifests through a diverse array of mediums, including literature, visual arts, music, and philanthropic endeavors. These multifaceted expressions of 'pakikibaka' share a common objective which is to disseminate the ideals of societal change and to serve as vehicles for enlightenment, particularly for individuals who may be misinformed or blinded to the veracity of certain truths.

"...Maraming porma sa pakikibaka sa perspective ko...merong pakikibaka na nakikita natin sa lansangan, meron pakikibaka na dinadaan sa pagsulat, meron pakikibaka na dinadaan sa sining, meron pakikibaka na dinadaan sa ano kawanggawa mga ganun... mga type. Pero yung pinaka center lang naman is...makagawa ng kolektibong pagbabago..." - SA 0006

FACTORS CONSIDERED BY STUDENT ACTIVISTS IN THEIR PAKIKIBAKA

Most youths in the present time are socially inclined and well-informed about what is happening in society. They are exposed to news about rampant corruption in the government, political issues, and economic concerns that affect the country and its people, especially those in marginalized sectors and those deprived of human rights. Through the internet and social media, students gained access to information that made them socially and politically informed. In addition, as they educated themselves about what is happening in society, they realized that people are fed with misinformation and have become victims of false information and propaganda. They became the vulnerable society that those in power openly exploited. Along the way, this awakening of social consciousness intensified their belief that something has to be done to change the system and how people think to achieve a changed society.

Inspired by their personal and family experiences

The motivation for student activists to participate in 'pakikibaka', is frequently derived from their personal and familial backgrounds. It is common for individuals to derive inspiration and acquire significant life lessons from their personal life adventures, especially when these experiences have had a tremendous influence on their lives. In this particular setting, numerous student activists have ascribed their dedication to 'pakikibaka' to their individual observations of the adversities experienced by their family members or close relatives.

"ako gusto ko ng mundo na di na mararanasan ng mga susunod na generation yung paghihirap na naranasan ng mga magulang ko kasi syempre di naman natin mag-glorify yung resiliency kasi syempre deserve naman natin mabuhay ng walang paghihirap na nasa atin ang resources at di natin kailangan na kumayod ng bongga para mabuhay at may ipakain sa family..." - SA 005

The direct exposure to familial struggles has provided these activists with a profound and personal understanding of the type of life they believe future generations deserve. This intimate connection with familial adversity has become a source of inspiration that gives meaning to their endeavors as student activists with deep purpose and significance.

Getting experiences from the masses

The engagement of student activists with the masses serves as a fundamental cornerstone of their 'pakikibaka'. Central to their experiences is the conviction that they are not solitary actors in the endeavor to combat injustices and draw attention to those who

exploit and marginalize the impoverished segments of society due to their perceived lack of agency and capacity to assert their rights.

"Hindi namin pinagtatangol...kasama namin ang masa. Nakikisama kami sa kanilang tunggalian sa lipunan at iniintindi namin diba parang ano ba talaga yung kalagayan nila..paano kami makakatulong..." - SA 0003

Involvement of Courage in Pakikibaka

The involvement of courage is an inherent and indispensable facet of 'pakikibaka', particularly within the context of activist engagement in high-risk scenarios, which includes 'red-tagging'. This term refers to the practice of labeling individuals or groups as belonging to subversive or insurgent organizations, often with negative consequences. Despite the inherent risks, there persist individuals who steadfastly advocate for the noble and unadulterated aspirations of the masses, exhibiting a profound and enduring commitment to their cause.

"...ayun nga kasi yung community namin noon sa holy may pulis doon...diba simbahan siya tapos may pulis tapos medyo...tingin tingin din kami...ganyan tapos may mga kasama din tapos may isa kaming kasama pag uwi sabi "ni redtag ako...NPA daw ako" Pero ayun kapag ganon hindi na siya kumbaga nakakatakot...na katulad nung una na parang mas dedma na ganun. Pero may time din kasi na ako e, ang lala ng redtagging...na lalaban ka talaga." - SA 0005

Pakikibaka aims for Social Transformation

'Pakikibaka' fundamentally aspires toward social transformation. Student activists steadfastly adhere to this ideology, driven by an unwavering commitment to effect meaningful change within society. This stance is anchored in a comprehensive social reformation of systems, beliefs, and improved governance that always aims for the people's benefit and welfare, especially that of the poor and unprivileged. These student activists amplify the voices of the marginalized, not for themselves, but for the unheard voices of the masses who cannot stand for their rights because of fear and lack of knowledge.

"diba ika nga...the philosophers either to have only interpreted the world...the point, however, is to change it..." at yun...yun yung para sa akin pinaka cracks na panimula ng pagsali ko sa ganitong kilusan na hindi ka lang nagsusuri para lang may maipasa...para lang makapagrecite..nagsusuri ka para may mabago ka...para pangahasan mo na talaga diba bumalik sa lipunan..." - SA 003

EFFECT OF PAKIKIBAKA ON THE EXPERIENCES OF THE STUDENT ACTIVIST

The concept of 'pakikibaka' holds profound significance in the lives of student activists, exerting a transformative influence across various dimensions of their existence. 'Pakikibaka' represents their active engagement in a range of initiatives, primarily geared towards amplifying the voices of the oppressed masses. This involvement, however, cannot be extricated from their broader way of life, encompassing their roles as students, individuals, and members of society.

As Student

In the role of a student, the concept of "pakikibaka" assumes profound significance in the lives of student activists. It serves as a transformative force, not merely confined to their academic pursuits but extending into their broader understanding of the world and their responsibilities as informed individuals.

Knowledge regarding social issues

Despite their relative youth and limited life experiences, student activists confront the harsh realities of the world, serving as a catalyst for the evolution of their perspectives on societal events. 'Pakikibaka' serves as a beacon illuminating their views on social issues, underscoring its role in broadening their understanding.

"...kaya if may nakukuha man ako it's the fact na makakahanap ako ng community within pakikibaka... nakikita mo talaga kung gaano ka-integral kasi yung roles ng society when it comes to... development of mental illnesses...stressors...maganda din siya[ng] perspective...so kung may nakukuha man ako it's the community and the perspective ..." - SA 0006

By giving the oppressed a voice, activists encouraged their kapwa that there is still a way to improve their lives and support others.

"...hindi siya actually nakakadistract...like again sinabi ko nga na nabibigyan siya ng halaga lalo in purpose na hindi lang ako nag-aaral dahil in the future maging capitalist slave ako...like parang may hope pala na mag-aaral ako kasi in the future pag naging ganito ako...pwede kong maibigay yung serbisyo ko sa masang nangangailangan..." - SA 0006

Participating in different forms of activism, like educational discussions, paved the way to making them realize that they needed to speak for those who could not speak for themselves.

Provide an impression of educational situations

After being exposed to different difficulties with their studies, they were forced to see what was happening, not only in their struggles but also what is happening in their environment.

"Nakikita ko na ang academic freedom na nire-repress po...di po ako natatakot rather ang binibigay po saking effect ay mas kumikilos

po ako, mas naa-agitate po yung willingness ko na lumaban." - SA 0002

Providing purpose and discipline as a student

Participation in student activism stimulates students to gain information and develop discipline. Despite the opinions of others, it is apparent that the fundamental lessons they learned from pakikibaka aid in transforming themselves and comprehending others.

"... Syempre dinidisciplina ko na talaga na mag aral and ina-assure ko...na enough yung performance ko...na para masabi ng parents ko na... 'okay kahit madami kang ginagawa kahit lumalayo ka kahit saan yung performance mo as a student' yun pa rin..." - SA 0004

As an Individual

On a personal level, 'pakikibaka' exerts a multifaceted influence on the lives of student activists, touching upon their fears, career considerations, family dynamics, and their sense of purpose and discipline. It shapes their identities, fostering empathy and resilience in the face of challenges.

Fear and Concerns

Engagement in "pakikibaka" often engenders fears regarding personal safety, future career prospects, and family relationships. This commitment to fighting for the marginalized masses can disrupt the personal lives of student activists.

Career

Engagement in "pakikibaka" prompts individuals to be cautious in their expressions, especially on social media, and can have repercussions on future employment prospects. This awareness shapes their political convictions and academic focus:

"...So mas careful ako in a sense na hindi ako padaskol daskol sa mga sinasabi ko sa social media pero at the same time mas pinalakas din yung paninindigan ko sa politikal na aspeto pati sa akademiko kumbaga noon research ako ng research pero hindi ko naman alam kung para saan...kumbaga for credentials lang...pero ngayon may tunguhin na..." - SA 0003

Family Relationships

Student activists often grapple with strained familial relationships, as their activism may be met with resistance or misunderstandings from family members:

"...yung tatay ko kasi ayaw niya talaga sa aktibista eh like ano..may mga panahon na nirered tag niya ako outright ganyan..kaya tinawag niya nga akong terorista...kaya talagang naapektuhan ako...mentally, emotionally kasi tatay mo nirered tag ka..." - SA 0006

Providing purpose and discipline as Individuals

Participation in 'pakikibaka' has played a role in their transformation and enhanced self-awareness. Student activists gain a deeper understanding of the struggles faced by their fellow citizens, honing their ability to navigate both their own challenges and their role as advocates:

"...yung pagkakaroon ng purpose...kasi kung [ang] pagbabasehan mo materyal...wala talaga siya e. siguro makakuha ka ng libreng stickers sa mga kasama, pero wala talaga...mas sa sarili siya parang panibagong hubog...ganon tapos alam naman natin na kapag napagtagumpayan...lahat naman tayo magbe-benefit..." - SA 0005

As a Member of the Society

Beyond their individual experiences, student activists engage with 'pakikibaka' as active members of society, becoming more attuned to the political landscape, societal structures, and their profound implications for the masses. Their activism is directed toward systemic change, underscoring their commitment to social justice and equality.

Give information on the current political environment

Participation in 'pakikibaka' immerses student activists in the sociopolitical milieu, fostering a heightened awareness of the country's political dynamics and its implications for the masses. Their activism is not directed against individuals but rather against the systemic structures that perpetuate inequality:

"...kahit sinong iupo mo dyan...systemic kasi yan eh...hindi sya basta sa personalidad. Kaya ang aming puna ay syempre yung kabuuan ng lipunan...hindi pwedeng puro tao lang. Kaya doon nagkakatunggali. Pananatilihin ba natin tong lipunan kasi okay na eh diba? Kaso ang tanong namin bilang nasa kaliwa...sino yung nakikinabang sa sistemang to at sino yung mga pinagsasamantalahan para mapanatili tong sistemang to..." - SA 0003

Engagement with their Kapwa

The concept of 'pakikibaka' is a form of engagement with the oppressed masses through pakikipamahay, allowing them to experience life alongside the people they serve. Student activists gain a better understanding of the varied experiences of their kapwa from various

walks of life. This is also one of the foundations of their learning that reinforces their involvement in the "pakikibaka".

"...Sa community natin oo masaya tayo kapag nasa political rally tapos nakakapag communicate tayo sa ibang tao tulad ni Tatay Elmer...sa mga jeepney drivers...sa may Pasay na random strangers...basta-basta mo lang sila nakakausap...yung mga nagsasalita sa political rallies na labandera, mga fishermen, o kaya mga street vendors...masaya sila kausap nakakaantig sila sa puso..." - SA 0001

ASPIRATIONS OF STUDENT ACTIVISTS RELATED TO THEIR PAKIKIBAKA

The contemporary political landscape, particularly within the Philippines, is marked by a profound sense of uncertainty, underscoring the context in which student activists engage in their pakikibaka. This socio-political context is characterized by divergent ideologies, contrasting viewpoints, and multifaceted actions that influence the nation's social fabric. Despite the often disheartening conditions reminiscent of historical epochs, the individuals actively involved in pakikibaka alongside their kapwa continue to harbor expansive dreams, aspirations, and an unwavering commitment to their respective political ideologies.

Applying theories into practice

Activism is not only concerned with theory but also with putting it into practice. One of the primary responsibilities of activists is to initiate activities that integrate the theories of each discipline and apply them to different forms of struggle based on the condition of the masses in which they live and work.

"...hindi lang kami sa larangan ng politikainterdisiplinaryo...pangahasan mo...magbasa ng sosyolohiya...PolSci,... Even pieces of literature...even pieces of journalistic works are able to enlighten people... baguhin yung lipunan..of course diba...sumama...makiisa dun sa mga masa diba para sa akin diba let's affirm that practice and let's develop it..." - SA 003

This is consistent with the findings of J. Kellstadt's (2001) study, cited by Bevington and Dixon (2005), in which he asserted that different theories must be implemented, particularly in relation to each other.

Continue to comprehend the struggle and experience of their Kapwa

Although the participants have a degree of ambiguity with their kapwa, such as their family or close friends, it is part of their pakikibaka to pursue recognizing and being involved in their situation and current circumstances. Despite their differences, acknowledging their kapwa is a crucial component of their pakikibaka.

"...but at the end of the day, kasama sila sa pinaglalaman natin. Kaunting exercise tayo ng class consciousness...doon mo iredirect kasi at the end of the day...it's your responsibility na i-enlighten sila. Yung radikal na pagmamahal shouldn't and wouldn't stop sa election lang." - SA 0001

'Pakikibaka' is also viewed as an integral part of their lives that can be used in the future. Living among the masses and participating in different educational discussions shaped their fundamental perspective and comprehension of the experiences of the masses. They can use this essential knowledge to expand their views and assist their kapwa.

"...hindi lang naman siya puro rally inaaral mo rin kasi yung sitwasyon nang lipunan kaya nga tayo ano eh nagpapakum diba pangunahing kursong masa para maintindihan natin bakit ganito ba yung society, bakit pa ganito yung nararanasan natin ano ba tong ganyan... ganyan. like we educate to understand pero somehow so sa perspektibo lang rin kung paano naapektuhan nang pakikibaka" - SA 0006

Pakikibaka is the basis for a student activist's day-to-day life and existence. This becomes the foundation for acknowledging the condition of their kapwa and their ongoing pakikibaka despite the political climate of the country and the contradictions they are experiencing.

"Madadala ko po ang pakikibaka sa hinaharap kasi sa personal po ay constant to. Ang isa sa hindi mananakaw sayo ay prinsipyo at edukasyon kaya kapag araw-araw kahit na sabihin na "ay busy si kasama, hindi sya muna makakasama sa mobilization"...okay lang yon dahil nandyan pa rin yung mga napag-aralan, yung pag-iisip at yung prinsipyo...madadali pa rin po ito sa hinaharap, sa kinabukasan." - SA 002

Continue pakikipagkapwa with comrades in pakikibaka

A significant aspect of pakikibaka is the relationships formed within each group. Despite their differences, their knowledge, experience, and political ideology bind them together. Solid relationships and pakikipagkapwa are regarded as essential facets of pakikibaka as this unites every student activist, even though some individuals maintain a distance due to their current circumstances.

"...hindi lang siya collective living...but also collective understanding...alam ko yung collectivity kung isusumarize ko siya...yung organization that I'm in or like that community is very collective...hindi ko siya madiscribe e, hindi din kayo friends...hindi din kayo workmates...pero just exist together kasi bonded kayo ng ideology and daily understanding kung bakit niyo ba ginagawa, bakit ba kayo nagsasakripisyo..." - SA 006

Continue the pakikibaka with the masses

It is essential to consider pakikibaka since it relates not only to what is being done presently but also to what can be done in the future. It is critical to maintain the continuity of the pakikibaka in order to assert what they are fighting for. It is also associated with the continuation of the pakikibaka of those who fought for our present-day rights in the past.

"...it is our duty to remember... [na] di napuputol lang din yung pakikibaka nila hindi naman sa wala silang halaga pero hindi siya ma continue in a sense kasi wala nang mag-aalala eh kung walang makaalala sino ang gagalaw for them hindi naman na sila makapagsasalita kasi patay na sila yung ganon...so it's our duty as a youth to continue the revolve or the fight that was began before we came.." - SA 006

One of the goals of student activists is to have full-time engagement with their pakikibaka through maintaining their participation in mass activities and expanding their ranks.

"Gusto ko po kasi talaga yung sa mga full-time organizers na gusto ko rin mag participate sa mga protest, rally, gusto ko rin sa mga physical educational discussion, at the same time gusto ko din talaga magparticipate sa mga basic mass integration,... nag-house-to-house, gusto kong tumulong in a community level." - SA 001

By participating in the pakikibaka, they hope to aid in the development of their society and the next generation. This is one of the participants' leading aspirations and a primary motivation for joining the pakikibaka.

"...Siguro masasabi ko na ang paningin ko sa lipunan ivu-view ko siya critically in a way na alam ko may igaganda pa at ibubuhos ko lahat ng energy ko sa pakikibaka para masiguradong may igaganda pa ang society na ito para sa susunod na generation..."

Conclusions

This research illustrates the lived experiences of student activists and how they define their participation in pakikibaka. These experiences, as documented in the shared experiences of the participants, encompass a spectrum of sentiments, both positive and negative, reflecting the multifarious perspectives held by individual participants. The study serves to underscore that pakikibaka is perceived as a strategic avenue through which marginalized populations can be assisted and their fundamental rights advocated for. This facilitates their understanding of the struggles faced by their kapwa and motivates them to initiate various programs in multifarious expressive modalities, encompassing writing, visual arts, and music, among others.

Numerous student activists have become deeply involved in pakikibaka, and were driven by their personal encounters and those of their families. Within this cohort, there exist those who actively seek to accrue knowledge and insights from the masses, as well as cultivate appropriate responses after being subjected to red-tagging. Yet, it is their overarching aspiration for societal transformation or revolution that serves as the principal motivation behind their engagement in pakikibaka. As an individual well-versed in the lived realities of marginalized communities, a student activist attempts to disseminate this knowledge among their kapwa and spearhead a collective endeavor aimed at enhancing their quality of life.

Student activists should not undermine their credibility due to their status as students, individuals, and active members of society. Student activists perceive pakikibaka as a means to get a deeper understanding of social concerns and evaluate the prevailing educational climate. Similarly, they develop a sense of purpose and discipline as they progress in their academic journey. However, they have experienced some level of apprehension, particularly when considering their personal safety, prospects for future employment, and navigating familial relationships.

Contemplating the future, specifically with regard to their objectives and ambitions, student activists aim to employ the theoretical frameworks derived from pakikibaka and persist in their understanding of the struggle and shared experiences of their Kapwa. Furthermore, their intention is to persist in the pursuit of pakikibaka with the masses.

The overarching goal of this study is to examine the present challenges faced by individuals participating in this movement, with a particular focus on student activists, during a time of uncertainty. In doing so, we endeavor to furnish insights that can guide future advocates in their efforts to facilitate change and prioritize their engagements effectively. The inclusion of relevant material regarding the genuine experiences of the student activists throughout the pakikipagkwentuhan serves the noble purpose of aiding future studies in acquiring a more comprehensive recognition of the experiences and knowledge imparted by the student activists amidst this moment characterized by uncertainty.

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